

THE SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASES OF PRODUCTION COSTS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract:

This article analyzes the scientific-theoretical and methodological foundations of production costs in the digital economy and explores issues related to reducing costs in farm enterprises.

Keywords: innovative agrotechnologies, production, costs, quality, production cost, agriculture, enterprise, economic efficiency.

Introduction:

In the context of the digital economy, continuously increasing the economic efficiency of existing agricultural enterprises is considered an objective necessity. This is because the population in our country continues to grow each year, which requires the efficient use of intensive methods of production. The final result of intensive methods is a competitive product, which is characterized by high quality and low production costs.

Numerous scientific studies have been conducted to improve product quality, and practical results are being achieved. However, reducing production costs has become the central issue of today's economy. The reason for this is the large disproportion between the state procurement prices for agricultural products and the increasing costs of resources used for their production. Therefore, optimizing production costs and achieving economic efficiency through producing the most and highest quality products at the lowest possible costs is one of the most important economic issues.

During the reform process, a number of measures have been implemented by the government. For example, to further increase crop yields and labor productivity in the agricultural sector, the President of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, approved the strategy for the development of agriculture in Uzbekistan for the years 2020-2030.

The strategy outlines key measures, including the diversification of production, the creation of a favorable agribusiness environment, and the implementation of advanced technologies. On January 28, 2022, the President of Uzbekistan signed a decree regarding the "Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan for the Years 2022-2026."

Based on these developments, the topic chosen by the author for scientific research is considered highly relevant. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's decree of October 23, 2019, "On Approving the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture in Uzbekistan for 2020-2030," along with the Presidential decrees regarding the introduction of market principles in cotton cultivation and the improvement of certification systems in agriculture, all aim to ensure that agricultural enterprises produce higher quality products at lower costs, thereby ensuring their stability.

The main goal of these legal documents is to ensure the sustainability of agricultural enterprises by producing more and higher-quality products at the lowest cost. The issue of

reducing the production cost of agricultural products has been widely studied by researchers and practitioners.

In recent years, the disproportion between the prices of agricultural products and the prices of industrial goods used in agriculture has led to the need for further improvement of state support for the agricultural sector in line with market demands. This, in turn, has resulted in the production costs of agricultural products exceeding the required level.

The development of the national economy and the increase in the material welfare of workers are closely linked to the reforms being implemented not only in the economic sector but also in various social sectors. In this regard, increasing the volume of produced products, improving their quality, and, most importantly, gradually optimizing production costs play a critical role.

Research Methods:

Material costs account for the main part of production costs and play a significant role in shaping the cost of the products being produced. Therefore, ensuring the effective use of material costs in cotton and wheat production within state orders is essential for ensuring optimal efficiency in farm enterprises. To address these issues, scientific and practical considerations regarding how material costs are managed in farm enterprises are discussed in the context of an example of a specific farm.

Scientific Findings:

The results of the research provide scientific-practical recommendations for optimizing costs in farm enterprises and methods for evaluating the factors influencing these costs. These theoretical approaches can contribute to the development of knowledge and skills in the field and can serve as a basis for the development of regional and district programs, as well as the identification of practical measures.

The efficient, rational use of material, labor, and financial resources is key to reducing production costs, minimizing waste, increasing income, and improving the level of organization in production. However, qualified labor resources, modern machinery and technology, and high-quality raw materials will not automatically transform into useful final products. For this, it is necessary to organize production and labor efficiently, which involves creating safe working conditions, easing the workload, saving time, and enhancing labor culture.

In organizing labor, achievements in fields such as technology, engineering, biology, sociology, and pedagogy are utilized. Therefore, the mere availability of resources does not solve all problems; they must be directed towards sectors that maximize economic benefit. Uzbekistan, rich in various natural resources, requires effective capital and management to address this task.

Conclusions:

Changes in the quantity of resources used in the production process are divided into short-term and long-term periods. A short-term period refers to the period in which the enterprise can change the level of its use of fixed production capacity. The production process is a universal category, common to all stages of human development, all countries, nations, and peoples. It has evolved from the simplest hunting and farming tools to the most complex modern technologies used in industries like robotics, aviation, and telecommunications.

Currently, hundreds of industries and sectors in Uzbekistan produce essential goods and equipment for both consumption and production, such as in agriculture, industry, transport,

construction, and services. Every country seeks to develop industries that are necessary and suitable for its stage of development, considering the limited nature of resources.

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